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New location of the known corals genera (*Favosites* Lamarck, 1816 and *Halysites* Fischer von Waldheim, 1828) in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the new location of the known corals genera: *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816 and *Halysites* von Waldheim, 1828, in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland. These corals were obtained as a result of many years of exploration in this mine, by searching individual lots of post-glacial materials extracted by this mine.

Keywords: *Favosites*, *Halysites*, Mielenko Drawskie, post-glacial materials, Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, fossilized coral, palaeontological corals, palaeozoic corals

1. INTRODUCTION

Favosites are an extinct genus of coral that occurred from the Ordovician to the Late Permian. *Halysites* is an extinct genus of coral that occurred from the Ordovician to the Devonian. Corals fossils of the genera *Favosites* and *Halysites* can be found in sedimentary rocks almost all over the world.

***Favosites* morphology**

Favosites were found in colonies, branch-shaped, with funnel-shaped calyces composed of corallites in the form of prismatic tubes with polygonal cross-sections. Corallites are

connected by mural pores. Tabulae are numerous tightly arranged. The entire colony was usually oval, resembled a honeycomb, and lived in shallow waters.

***Halysites* morphology**

The colony consisted of long tubes connected laterally by narrower sides. Numerous densely arranged tabulae, no mural pores and structures resembling septae. Corallites in the form of tubes with a circular or oval cross-section.

Occurrence of fossilised corals in Poland

Fossilised corals can be found in solid sedimentary rocks in the Świętokrzyskie Mountains. In northern Poland, they are often found in post-glacial sediments, transported in the Pleistocene by the ice sheet from Scandinavia.

2. RESULT

Maps 1-4 show the location of the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland.

Photos 1-4 show the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland (photos taken by Tomasz Borowski).

Photos 5-13 show the known coral genera *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816, from the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland (photos taken by Tomasz Borowski).

Photos 14-17 show the known coral genera *Halysites* von Waldheim, 1828, from the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland (photos taken by Tomasz Borowski).

Paleontological systematics [taxonomy]

Kingdom: Animalia

Phylum: Cnidaria

Class: Anthozoa

Subclass: Tabulata

Order: Favositida

Family: Favositidae

Genus: *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

Kingdom: Animalia

Phylum: Cnidaria

Class: Anthozoa

Subclass: Tabulata

Order: Halysitida

Family: Halysitidae

Genus: *Halysites* Fischer von Waldheim, 1828

3. CONCLUSION

The new discovery site of the palaeozoic corals of the genus *Favosites* & *Halysites* in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland is documented and entered into the world map of the species distribution.

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Map 1. Location of the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenka Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland.

Map 2. Location of the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenka Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Map 3. Location of the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenka Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Map 4. Location of the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenka Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 1. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
West Pomeranian Province, Poland

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Photo 3. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
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Photo 4. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 5. The palaeozoic coral of the genus *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

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